

WP1 Shared modelling framework and learnings

D1.2 – Description of scientific methods

Task 1.3 Methods for Life Cycle Impact Assessment

Appendix – Mathematical model for calculating AGTP functions (Tier3)

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PROJECTS DETAILS			
Project title		Aligning Life Cycle Assessment methods and bio-based sectors for improved environmental performance.	
Project acronym	ALIGNED	Start / Duration	01/10/2022 – 36 months
Type of Action	RIA	Website	www.alignedproject.eu

This appendix details the mathematical model used to estimate AGTP functions. It is a simplified version from CCI Tool (Climate Change Impact tool for dynamic LCA). The complete version of CCI Tool is freely available online or for download at <https://www.insa-toulouse.fr/cci-tool/>.

The model was simplified and adapted to the ALIGNED context. Expert practitioners accustomed with Tier 3 results and willing to fine-tune CC impacts are invited to use the CCI Tool.

As compared to the original model, simplifications include:

- Only CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O gases are included, whereas CCI Tool includes other GHGs and short-lived climate forcers.
- Fossil and non-fossil CH₄ are not differentiated: the contribution to methane-emission metrics from CO₂ from fossil methane oxidation is not accounted.
- The AGTP function of a gas is computed independently from the other climate forcers, whereas CCI tool includes the dynamic interactions between all climate forcers.

Calculations and computed values can be found in 'AGTP functions.xlsx' file. Results were compared to IPCC values found in AR6 Table 7.SM.6 : relative differences amounted between 8% and 16% for CO₂ and N₂O, 1% for CH₄ AGTP50 and 33% for CH₄ AGTP100. Therefore, the simplified model may lack robustness to estimate long-term impacts in case of significant methane emissions.

Convolution operator

As an example, let's consider an exemplary cause-effect chain, e.g. emission A involves effect B. If effect B is defined over time it means that a 'pulse' A at $t=T_0$ would lead to an effect B(t) between T_0 and a given time horizon T_H . In impact assessment, the overall impact of pulse A would be defined as the cumulated effect of B over time.

However, when A is not a pulse emission but a time-distributed emission, a specific operator is necessary to consider the cumulative effect of all emissions between T_0 and a T_H .

In this case, the convolution product is used. It is noted with an * operator between function. For continuous functions f and g defined between 0 and H:

$$\forall t \in [0: H], (f * g)(t) = \int_0^t f(t') \cdot g(t - t') dt' \quad (1)$$

The convolution product is commutative, associative, distributive and supports scalar multiplication. Therefore, its manipulation is similar to the multiplication of scalar numbers, but adapted for 1-dimension functions such as temporal distributions.

In numerical application, discrete convolution of f and g - defined as a suite of values between year 0 and year n - is given by:

$$(f * g)(n) = \sum_{k=0}^n f(k) \cdot g(n - k) \quad (2)$$

The latter formula is used for numerical application of climate cause-effect chains, coupling emission profiles, GHG lifetimes, temporal influence of radiative forcing on temperature change, and carbon cycle feedback loops -as details in the coming sub-sections.

AGTP

The Absolute Global Temperature change Potential (AGTP) of substance X is a function over time labelled $AGTP_X(t)$. It is the sum of temperature change from direct radiating forcing of X over time ($AGTP_{d_X}$) and from the additional radiative forcing triggered by a change in CO_2 concentration ($AGTP_{cc_X}$) due to the change in temperature $AGTP_{d_X}$:

$$AGTP_X(t) = AGTP_{d_X}(t) + AGTP_{cc_X}(t) \quad (3)$$

These two terms are further described in the sections below.

Direct AGTP

AGTP_{d_x}(t) is defined as the convolution product between direct radiative forcing of X (RF_{d_x}) between 0 and t and the Impulse-temperature response function IRFT between 0 and t:

$$AGTP_{d_x}(t) = (RF_{d_x} * IRFT)(t) = \int_0^t RF_{d_x}(t') \cdot IRFT(t - t') dt' \quad (4)$$

IRFT is not substance-dependent. It is calculated as:

$$IRFT(t) = \frac{c_1}{d_1} e^{-\frac{t}{d_1}} + \frac{c_2}{d_2} e^{-\frac{t}{d_2}} \quad (5)$$

Parameters for IRFT function are retrieved from AR6 section 6.SM.2 and given in Table 1:

Table 1: parameters for Impulse-Response Temperature Function

Parameter	value	unit
c₁	0.44	°C/W/m ²
d₁	3.4	yrs
c₂	0.32	°C/W/m ²
d₂	285	yrs

Direct radiative forcing of substance X over time is defined as the convolution product of three functions: radiative efficiency $A_X(t)$, in W/m²/kg; impulse-response function of substance X IRF_X(t); and the temporal distribution of substance X flows $g_X(t)$:

$$RF_{d_X}(t) = (A_X * IRF_X * g_X)(t) \quad (6)$$

For small emission changes, the radiative efficiency of GHGs is considered as constant (AR6 chapter 7.6.1.2):

$$\forall t' \in [0: t], A_X(t') = A_X \quad (7)$$

$g_X(t)$ is the time-distributed flow of substance X. In the present calculation, $g_X(t)$ is shaped to represent a pulse function at year 0:

$$g_X(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } t = 0 \\ 0 & \text{for } t > 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Using equations (6), (7) and (8), RF_{d_x}(t) can be simplified as:

$$RF_{d_X}(t) = A_X \cdot IRF_X(t) \quad (9)$$

A_x are given in IPCC report as expressed in $W/m^2/ppbv$ (AR6 Table 7.SM.7). They are converted in $W/m^2/kg$ as follows:

$$A_{X_{kg}}(W/m^2/kg) = \frac{M_{atm} (g/mol)}{M_X (g/mol)} * \frac{1E9 (ppb/kg)}{T_m (kg)} * A_{X_{ppb}}(W/m^2/ppb) \quad (10)$$

Where M_{atm} , M_X , T_m are the molar mass of air, the molar mass of substance X, and total mass of the atmosphere, respectively. Values for equation (10) are given in Table 2:

Table 2: parameters related to radiative efficiency of CO_2 , CH_4 and N_2O

Parameter	unit	value	
M_{atm}	28.96	g/mol	
T_m	5.15E+18	kg	
Gas	Molar mass (g/mol)	A ($W/m^2/ppb$)	A ($W/m^2/kg$)
CO_2	44.0087	0.0000133	1.699E-15
CH_4	16.04206	0.000388	1.185E-13
N_2O	44.0124	0.0032	4.089E-13

The Impulse-response function of substance X (IRF_X) expresses the evolution of residual X in the atmosphere over time, following a pulse emission at year 0. It is a specific function for CO_2 , CH_4 and N_2O :

$$IRF_{CO_2}(t) = a_0 + a_1 \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_1}} + a_2 \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_2}} + a_3 \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_3}} \quad (11)$$

$$IRF_{CH_4}(t) = a_{CH_4} \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_{CH_4}}} = (1 + f_1 + f_2) \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_{CH_4}}} \quad (12)$$

$$IRF_{N_2O}(t) = a_{N_2O} \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_{N_2O}}} = \left(1 - 0.36 \cdot (1 + f_1 + f_2) \cdot \frac{A_{CH_4}}{A_{N_2O}}\right) \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_{N_2O}}} \quad (13)$$

Parameters for IRF_{CO_2} were left unchanged between AR5 and AR6. They can be found in AR5 Table 8.SM.10. Parameters for equations (12) and (13) originate from AR5 (8.SM.11.3), except for CH_4 and N_2O lifetimes, updated in AR6 Table 7.SM.7. Values for IRF functions used here are displayed in Table 3 and Table 4:

Table 3: parameters of IRF function for CO_2

a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3
0.2173	0.224	0.2824	0.2763
	τ_1 (yrs)	τ_2 (yrs)	τ_3 (yrs)
	394.4	36.54	4.304

Table 4: parameters of IRF function for CH₄ and N₂O

Parameter	value	unit
A_{CH₄} (ppbv)	0.000388	W/m ² /ppbv
A_{N₂O} (ppbv)	0.0032	W/m ² /ppbv
f₁	0.5	-
f₂	0.15	-
τ_{CH₄}	11.8	yrs
τ_{N₂O}	109	yrs

Indirect AGTP induced by the carbon cycle response

$AGTP_{ccx}(t)$ is the temperature change induced by the “carbon cycle response” to a temperature change: an increase in temperature leads to an increase in CO₂ concentration, which in turns leads to an additional temperature change. $AGTP_{ccx}(t)$ is defined as the convolution product of the indirect radiative forcing due to the carbon cycle response to an emission of X (RF_{ccx}), with IRFT function (eq. 5):

$$AGTP_{ccx}(t) = (RF_{ccx} * IRFT)(t) \quad (14)$$

$RF_{ccx}(t)$ is the indirect radiative forcing induced by the carbon cycle response after a temperature change pulse. It is calculated using CO₂ radiative efficiency ACO_2 and the convolution product between $AGTPd_x$, the impulse response function of CO₂ flux perturbation ($\gamma RF(t)$) and $IRF_{CO_2}(t)$ (defined above):

$$RF_{ccx}(t) = (AGTPd_x * \gamma RF * AGTPd_{CO_2})(t) \quad (15)$$

When modelling a pulse emission profile (eq 8), the reader can verify than equations (14) and (15) are equivalent to IPCC equation 7.SM.5.5:

$$AGTP_{ccx}(t) = (AGTPd_x * \gamma RF * AGTPd_{CO_2})(t) \quad (16)$$

$\gamma RF(t)$ describes the change in CO₂ concentration in response to a unit temperature pulse:

$$\gamma RF(t) = \gamma \left(\delta(t) - \frac{\alpha_1}{\tau_{cc1}} \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_{cc1}}} - \frac{\alpha_2}{\tau_{cc2}} \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_{cc2}}} + \frac{\alpha_3}{\tau_{cc3}} \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_{cc3}}} \right) \quad (17)$$

Parameters for γRF are found in AR6 Table 7.SM.6 and listed in Table 5:

Table 5: parameters of the carbon cycle response function

Parameter	value	unit
γ	1.106E+13	kgCO ₂ /yr/°C
$\delta(t)$	1 for t=0 0 for t>0	-
α_1	0.638	-
α_2	0.3322	-
α_3	0.031	-
τ_{cc1}	2.376	yrs
τ_{cc2}	30.14	yrs
τ_{cc3}	490.1	yrs

Summary of Parameters

Parameter	value	unit	ref	used in equations
c_1	0.44	$^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{W}/\text{m}^2$	IPCC AR6 (6.SM.2)	(5)
d_1	3.4	yrs		
c_2	0.32	$^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{W}/\text{m}^2$		
d_2	285	yrs		
M_{atm}	28.96	g/mol	-	(8)
T_m	5.15E+18	kg		
M_{CO_2}	44.0087	g/mol		
M_{CH_4}	16.04206	g/mol		
$M_{\text{N}_2\text{O}}$	44.0124	g/mol		
A_{CO_2} (ppbv)	0.0000133	$\text{W}/\text{m}^2/\text{ppbv}$	IPCC AR6 Table 7.SM.7	(8)
A_{CH_4} (ppbv)	0.000388	$\text{W}/\text{m}^2/\text{ppbv}$		(8), (11)
$A_{\text{N}_2\text{O}}$ (ppbv)	0.0032	$\text{W}/\text{m}^2/\text{ppbv}$		(8), (11)
A_{CO_2} (kg)	1.69943E-15	$\text{W}/\text{m}^2/\text{kg}$	equation (8)	(13)
A_{CH_4} (kg)	1.18481E-13	$\text{W}/\text{m}^2/\text{kg}$		
$A_{\text{N}_2\text{O}}$ (kg)	4.08852E-13	$\text{W}/\text{m}^2/\text{kg}$		
a_0	0.2173	-	IPCC AR5 Table 8.SM.10	(9)
a_1	0.224	-		
a_2	0.2824	-		
a_3	0.2763	-		
τ_1	394.4	yrs		
τ_2	36.54	yrs		
τ_3	4.304	yrs		
f_1	0.5	-	IPCC AR5 (8.SM.11.3)	(10), (11)
f_2	0.15	-		
τ_{CH_4}	11.8	yrs	IPCC AR6 Table 7.SM.7	(10)
$\tau_{\text{N}_2\text{O}}$	109	yrs		(11)
γ	1.106E+13	$\text{kgCO}_2/\text{yr}/^{\circ}\text{C}$	IPCC AR6 Table 7.SM.6	(17)
$\delta(t)$	1 for $t=0$ 0 for $t>0$			
α_1	0.638	-		
α_2	0.3322	-		
α_3	0.031	-		
$\tau_{\text{cc}1}$	2.376	yrs		
$\tau_{\text{cc}2}$	30.14	yrs		
$\tau_{\text{cc}3}$	490.1	yrs		